

Mobility of Trace Elements in Soils by Thin Layer Chromatography : Part II—Influence of Salinity, Alkalinity, Phosphate and Organic Matter.

J. P. SINGHAL, (Mrs.) NAMITA SINGH and R. P. SINGH

Chemical Laboratories, Faculty of Engineering and Technology,
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh.

Manuscript received 26 July 1976 ; accepted 30 December 1976

The R_F values or mobilities of micronutrients in the two diverse soils as measured with the help of thin layer chromatography were found to be sensitive to salinity, alkalinity, phosphate and organic matter. These parameters resulted in marked variations in the movement of Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} in the soils. The results has been explained on the basis of certain interactions between the trace elements and the variables.

TRACE elements are recognised as essential for healthy development of animals, plants or microorganisms.

The mobility of such inorganic chemicals placed into or within the soil may influence their availability, effectiveness or potentiality for plant nutrition. Different salts and compounds, pH and electrical conductivity, ion exchange and adsorption are expected to affect the mass transfer, diffusion and leaching of micro-nutrients in soils. Of the several methods, thin layer chromatography has been used by Helling and Turner¹ and Helling^{2,3,4} as a tool for the study of pesticide mobility in soils. Rhodes, Belasco and Pease⁵ have made use of this technique and Freundlich constants for assessing absorption and leachability of agricultural chemicals in soils. Singhal and Singh⁶ have recently reported the effects of different leachates on the R_F values of trace elements in soils. In the present communication an effort has been made to study the influence of pH, electrical conductance, salinity, alkalinity, phosphate and organic matter on the mobility of micronutrients in soils with the help of thin layer chromatography. In view of the importance of the subject it was considered that such a study will prove useful.

Materials and Methods

The soils used in the investigations were surface samples (depth 0 to 30 cm) from the central lowland type III area of Aligarh district, and the Kota district of Rajasthan. The Aligarh soil was an alkaline solonetz and the Kota soil, a black cotton sample formed by weathering of metamorphic rocks. The relevant properties of the soils are summarized in table 1.

For thin layer chromatography, each soil was ground and sieved through a 100 mesh sieve to obtain samples with a nearly homogeneous particle size. Clean glass plates (20 x 20 cm) were taken and coated with a slurry of the soil at a thickness of 0.5 mm with the help of a TLC applicator. After the plates were dried at room temperature, two lines, at 3 cm and 13 cm above the base were scribed so that the standard development distance of 10 cm was used on all the plates. Pure chemicals were used for preparing 0.1M solutions of trace elements. The solutions were applied on the soil plates as spots using thin layer capillaries at a height of 3 cm. The plates were then developed with distilled water upto the upper line by ascending chromatography. In case of the plates coated with black cotton soil, wet stripes of filter paper about 2.5 cm wide, were wrapped around the bottom of the plates to prevent disintegration of the soil layer on contact with water.

The developed plates were allowed to air dry and the mobility of trace elements detected with the help of suitable detectors which were sprayed over the plates. Pure 1% diphenyl carbazide in alcohol for Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} ; 0.1% dimethylglyoxime in ammonia for Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} and 1% aqueous potassium ferrocyanide for Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and Cu^{2+} were used as detectors.

For a study of the effect of salinity, alkalinity, phosphate and organic matter on the mobility of trace elements, definite quantities of CaSO_4 , MgSO_4 , Na_2CO_3 , NaHCO_3 and Na_3PO_4 were mixed with the two soils in varying proportions, homogeneously, before making their slurry with distilled water. In case of

TABLE I — MECHANICAL COMPOSITION AND PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ALIGARH SOLONETZ AND KOTA BLACK COTTON SOILS

Soil type	Mechanical composition in percentage			pH	E. C. in mhos $\text{cm}^{-1} \times 10^{-2}$	BEC in meq per 100g.	Organic matter percentage
	Sand	Silt	Clay				
Aligarh type III	33.6	63.4	3.0	9.2	0.5	16.3	0.41
Kota black cotton	8.4	47.0	44.8	7.4	0.7	26.8	0.88

organic matter, a sample was prepared by adding humic acid in 0.1% proportion and another sample by removing organic matter with the help of 30 per cent H_2O_2 at low heat.

relationship :

$$R_F = \frac{1}{10} \frac{R_T + R_L}{2}$$

where R_T was the tailing front and R_L was the leading front. The results are recorded in Figs. 1 to 4. Line sketches of a few typical movements drawn according to scale are given in Fig. 5.

Mobilities were measured as R_F values from the

Fig. 1 Effect of salinity on pH, E.C. and R_F values of the Aligarh soils and Kota black cotton soil (dotted curves for Aligarh soil and continuous curves for Kota soil)

Fig. 3 Effect of Phosphate on pH, E.C. and R_F values of the Aligarh soils and Kota black cotton soils (dotted curves for Aligarh soil and continuous curves for Kota soil)

Fig. 2 Effect of alkalinity on pH, E.C. and R_F Values of the Aligarh soils and black cotton soils (dotted curves for Aligarh soil and continuous curves for Kota soil)

Fig 4 Effect of Organic matter on R_F Values of the Aligarh solonetz and Kota black cotton soils (dotted curves for Aligarh soil and continuous curves for Kota soil)

FIG 5 MOBILITY OF TRACE ELEMENTS IN SOILS IN PRESENCE OF SALINITY ALKALINITY, PHOSPHATE AND ORGANIC MATTER

Results and Discussion

An examination of the data (vide table 1) showed that the two soils selected for study were of diverse nature and origin. While the Aligarh soil exhibited the characteristics of a solonetz alluvial illitic silt loam with alkaline and saline characteristics, the Kota soil was a dark grey montmorillonitic silty clay with crumb structure and a low permeability.

Addition of saline ($MgSO_4$, $CaSO_4$), alkaline (Na_2CO_3 , $NaHCO_3$) and phosphate (Na_3PO_4) salts to the soils resulted in significant pH and electrical conductivity variations (Figs. 1-3). In most of the cases an inflection occurred in the pH and electrical conductance at 6 per cent of the added salt. This was indicative of the completion of an interaction between the soils and the salt leading to formation of Ca-, Mg-, Na- or phosphatic soils respectively.

Development of the micronutrient spots on the TLC soil plates with distilled water resulted in tailings and lateral movements (Fig. 5). Measurement of the R_F values of the elements indicated that a rise in salinity (Fig. 1) resulted in marked variation in the mobilities of micronutrients in Aligarh alluvial soil. The effect was lesser in black cotton soil. The results were in accordance with the work of Ellis and Coworkers⁷ who found higher diffusion rates of Cu^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} in illitic as compared to montmorillonitic clays. In all the cases, except Fe^{2+} , there was a rise in the mobility of the trace elements upto the point of saturation of the soils with Ca- or Mg- sulphates followed by a fall or constancy thereafter. The mobility of Fe^{2+} exhibited variable behaviour and Cu^{2+} became immobile in presence of $MgSO_4$. Ferric iron showed no movement either in the blank soil or with an increase in its salinity. The nutrients showing larger mobility exhibited larger

lateral diffusions (Fig. 5). Inflections occurred in the R_F values of the trace elements in the ranges of 6 to 8 per cent of the added saline salts and these were closely related to the pH and conductivity inflections (Fig. 1). The increase in the mobility of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} with increase in salinity appeared to be due to adsorptive effects and creation of an electrical potential in the soils that caused the cations to move forward. The decrease in pH was also responsible for increase in solubility and movement of the elements. Reverse effects occurred on saturation. Further saline conditions favoured oxidation transformations in Fe^{2+} system resulting in a reduction of its mobility to a saturation point.

The effect of alkalinity on the mobility of the trace elements in the soils is represented (vide Figs. 2 and 5). A great diversity is seen in the behaviour of the two

salts on the R_F values of the trace elements in the two soils. Thus while Na_2CO_3 produced a marked and characteristic increase followed by decrease in the R_F values of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} in the black cotton montmorillonitic loam, it had an almost opposite effect on the mobility of these elements in the alluvial illitic soil. Conversely NaHCO_3 increased the mobility of the above elements in the alluvial soil and decreased the effect in the black cotton soil. Ferrous iron was an exception and became immobile beyond 6% of alkaline salts. Ferric iron showed no movement in untreated or treated soils. Higher R_F values were accompanied by larger lateral diffusion movements. An inflection was produced in most of the curves at 6 per cent of the alkaline salts. The mobility variations of the elements showed marked correlations with the pH changes in the two soils. The diversity in the mobility effects by Na_2CO_3 and NaHCO_3 in the two soils (Fig. 2) could be due to the simultaneous operation of several factors such as the varied nature of precipitation and solubilising effects due to variation in pH , and a difference in the diffusion rates of the carbonates and bicarbonates of trace elements in the illitic and montmorillonitic soils. Further work is, however, needed to clarify these relationships.

Addition of Na_3PO_4 resulted in characteristic variation of the R_F values of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} in both the soils (Fig. 3). Thus while the R_F values of Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} showed an initial increase in the alluvial soil, those of Fe^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} decreased and exhibited a fluctuating pattern. All elements except Fe^{2+} became immobile in black cotton clay loam at and beyond 6 per cent Na_3PO_4 . Inflections occurred in the mobilities of all the micronutrients at 6 to 8 per cent of Na_3PO_4 added. As in the previous cases, a close correlation was observed between the mobilities and the pH variations in both the soils. An explanation for such a behaviour could be found in the fact that at pH values beyond 7, interactions occurred between the trace elements and the phosphate

leading to formation of complex insoluble phosphates which hindered the mobility of the elements to variable extents. The effect was intense in the montmorillonitic clay in case of all elements except Fe^{2+} , but fluctuated in the alluvial soil due to a variation in mineral composition and texture.

Organic matter too had a marked effect on the movement of trace elements. It resulted in an initial decrease, an inflection at 0.4% of organic matter, followed by a rise in the mobility in the alluvial soil. The effect was less pronounced though variable in the case of black cotton soil. Organic matter has a great effect on the adsorptive behaviour of a soil and by itself has a complexing tendency for the trace metals. These along with other factors may be responsible for the variation in the R_F values of the two soils on addition of organic matter.

Acknowledgement

The second and third authors are grateful for the award of a teacher fellowship and a post doctorate fellowship respectively, by the U.G.C. (India).

References

1. C. S. HELLING and B. C. TURNER, *Science*, 1968, 162, 562.
2. C. S. HELLING, *Soil. Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1971, 35, 732.
3. C. S. HELLING, *Soil. Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1971, 35, 737.
4. C. S. HELLING, *Soil. Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1971, 35, 743.
5. C. R. RHODES, I. J. BELASCO and H. L. PEASE, *J. Agri. Food. Chem.*, 1970, 18, 524.
6. J. P. SINGHAL and R. P. SINGH, *Kolloid zur Polym.*, 1977, 255, 488.
7. J. H. ELLIS, R. I. BRANHISEL and R. E. PHILLIPS, *Soil. Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1970, 34, 866.